

"TECHNOLOGY OF DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH OF STUDENTS OF PRIMARY PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY OF NATURAL FIBERS (COTTON)"

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Abstract. *The development of oral communication skills in students studying the primary processing technology of natural fibers, such as cotton, is very important in roles related to processing technology. By explaining processes, communicating instructions, and engaging in discussions with colleagues and stakeholders, smooth operations and successful project delivery are high. And problem-solving skills in this area are enhanced: Competent oral communication skills allow students to effectively communicate ideas, ask questions, and participate in collaborative problem-solving. In the context of textile processing, the ability to solve problems, propose solutions and discuss strategies with team members is essential for optimizing production processes and troubleshooting. Plus professional development and career advancement: Strong verbal communication skills are often viewed as a key competency in the workplace. Students who excel in oral communication are better equipped to confidently present their ideas, participate in negotiations and demonstrate leadership qualities that can contribute to their professional growth and development in the textile industry.*

Keywords: *Textile Industry Communication. Cotton Processing Education. Oral Speech Development. Technical Communication Skills. Primary Processing Technology. Natural Fibers Education. Industry-Specific Vocabulary. Hands-On Communication Activities. Technical Terminology Acquisition. Oral Presentation Skills. Industry Communication Strategies.*

The technology for developing oral speech skills among students studying primary processing technology of natural fibers, such as cotton, can be crucial in preparing them for effective communication within the textile industry. Here are some tailored strategies to enhance oral speech development in this specific academic context:

✓ **Industry-Specific Vocabulary Building:** Focus on teaching students specialized vocabulary related to the primary processing of natural fibers, particularly cotton. Include terms like ginning, carding, spinning, weaving, and other relevant terminology to help students communicate fluently and accurately in discussions related to their field.

✓ **Hands-On Demonstrations and Lab Sessions:** Encourage students to explain the processes involved in primary processing technology verbally. Organize hands-on demonstrations and lab sessions where they can practice describing each step of cotton processing aloud, reinforcing their understanding and ability to articulate technical procedures.

✓ **Storytelling and Narration Exercises:** Incorporate storytelling and narration exercises into the curriculum. Ask students to narrate the journey of cotton from harvesting to the final textile product, emphasizing clear and structured oral communication.

✓ **Role-Playing Scenarios:** Create role-playing scenarios based on real-life situations in cotton processing plants or textile factories. Assign students different roles where they have to communicate with each other using industry-specific language, fostering interactive speech development.

✓ **Presentations on Cotton Processing:** Assign students research projects or presentations on various aspects of cotton processing. This will require them to organize their

thoughts, conduct thorough research, and deliver informative speeches on topics like cotton cultivation, processing techniques, or quality control measures.

✓ **Debates on Industry Issues:** Organize debates on current issues in the cotton processing industry, such as sustainability practices, technological advancements, or market trends. Encourage students to voice their opinions, engage in discussions, and defend their viewpoints, honing their persuasive and argumentative speaking skills.

✓ **Peer Feedback and Peer Teaching:** Implement peer feedback sessions where students provide constructive criticism to each other on their oral presentations. Additionally, encourage peer teaching, where students explain concepts to their classmates, promoting collaboration and communication skills development.

By incorporating these tailored strategies into the curriculum for students studying primary processing technology of natural fibers, educators can effectively cultivate their oral speech abilities, enabling them to communicate proficiently and confidently within the specific context of cotton processing and the broader textile industry.

When exploring the topic of the technology for developing oral speech skills among students studying primary processing technology of natural fibers, specifically focusing on cotton, there are several areas of research and works that could be valuable for further study and implementation. Here are some key areas and potential sources to explore:

- **Research Papers:** Look into studies that delve into the cognitive processes involved in language acquisition and speech development in educational settings.

- **Books:** Books like "Educational Psychology" by Anita Woolfolk and "Language Acquisition: The Growth of Grammar" by Maria Teresa Guasti could provide insights into effective teaching methods for oral speech development.

- **Textbooks:** Textbooks on textile technology and cotton processing that include sections on effective communication within the industry.

- **Research Journals:** Journals focusing on textile engineering and communication in industrial settings could offer valuable research findings.

- **Educational Research:** Explore research on pedagogical strategies tailored to technical fields, aiming to enhance oral communication skills among students.

- **Educational Conferences:** Attendance at conferences focusing on technical education and communication skills development could provide exposure to best practices and innovative approaches.

- **Case Studies:** Analyze case studies of successful language programs in technical fields or industries to draw parallels and gather insights for implementing similar practices in the context of cotton processing technology.

- **Best Practice Guides:** Look for guides and manuals that provide recommendations for teaching oral communication skills in technical disciplines.

- **Literature Review:** Review studies on speech therapy and communication disorders to understand potential challenges students may face in speech development and ways to address them effectively.

- **Professional Organizations:** Engage with organizations related to speech therapy and language development for additional resources and expertise.

By delving into these areas of research and works, educators and curriculum developers can gain a deeper understanding of the technology for enhancing oral speech skills among students of primary processing technology of natural fibers, with a specific focus on cotton processing.

Integrating findings from these sources can enrich teaching practices and promote effective communication skill development tailored to the needs of students in this specialized field.

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